

A Record of Buddhist Monasteries in Luoyang

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Entry tags: Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Religious Group, Text, Buddhist Traditions, Chinese Buddhist text

Buddhists living in the imperial capital of Luoyang under the Northern Wei Dynasty of China in the fifth and sixth centuries, including monastics, foreign visitors, and laypeople (both nobility and commoners). A Record of Buddhist Monasteries in Luoyang (Chinese: Luoyang qielan ji, 洛陽伽藍記) was written in approximately 547 CE by Yang Xuanzhi (Chinese: 楊衒之 fl. 6th century CE) about the many Buddhist monasteries and temples that had formerly been present in the historic Chinese capital of Luoyang (modern Shaanxi province). Luoyang had been most recently rebuilt as the capital of the Northern Wei dynasty (386-535 CE), when Emperor Xiaowen (r. 471-499 CE) relocated the empire's capital there as part of his reforms and the city boasted over a thousand Buddhist temples in addition to imperial palaces and institutions of government. However, Luoyang had been largely destroyed amidst the destructive civil wars that marked the end of the Northern Wei, and by the time of Yang's writing, he noted that few temples remained, and sought to provide future generations with a record of their existence, along with stories associated with their presence. The Record is subdivided into five major sections covering temples located in the inner city, along with those in the suburbs, ordered by cardinal direction. Yang records detailed descriptions of the major temples present in Luoyang, including architectural details and functions of their buildings, their physical location within the city, and crucially, many political and cultural events associated with them. A typical entry for a temple would include its name, sponsors, construction date, and noteworthy aspects of its construction, especially landmarks such as towers and Buddhist images. The prose of the Record intersperses Yang's descriptions and accounts with notes on the individuals and events he describes, providing valuable insights into the religio-cultural and social life of the capital city during the early medieval period. The entries on individuals and events include prose noting major political upheavals such as rebellions and palace intrigues, as well as short biographies of people associated with the temple, both monastic and lay. The last section of the text focus on the northern suburbs of the city but also includes an extensive travelogue recounting a pilgrimage from 518-522 CE led by Northern Wei emissaries Song Yun and Hui Sheng to the Western Regions (modern Central Asia). Song and Hui's account also record cultural and religious traditions they observed in the cities of the areas they visited, including locations of Buddhist miracles, the religiosity of the rulers, and foreign relations between the countries. Yi-t'ung Wang's (Chinese: 王伊同) 1984 translation into English from Princeton University Press and W.J.F. Jenner's 1981 translation in *Memories of Loyang* are two complete versions of the work in English.

Date Range: 493 CE - 547 CE

Region: Han-Wei Luoyang

Region tags: China, Luoyang, Six Dynasties China, Early Medieval China

The imperial city of the newly rebuilt Luoyang under the Northern Wei, 495-535. Note that the modern course of the Luo River brings the river almost directly to the southern wall of the city, whereas in early medieval times it ran towards the south. The White Horse Temple (Baima Si), built during the Han, was located outside the city proper in its environs. This region depicts only the approximate area of the walled city.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yang, Xuanzhi, trans. Yi-t'ung Wang. *A Record of Buddhist Monasteries in Lo-Yang*. Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 1984.
- Source 2: Jenner, W. J. F. *Memories of Loyang: Yang Hsüan-Chih and the Lost Capital (493-534)*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1981.
- Source 3: Yang, Xuanzhi. *Luoyang qie lan ji*. Beijing: Zhonghua shu ju, 2020.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 Description: Not Applicable

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=gb&res=751279>
- Source 1 Description: Original text on CTEXT (中國哲學書電子化計劃).
- Source 2 URL: <https://zh.wikisource.org/zh-hant/%E6%B4%9B%>
- Source 2 Description: Original text on WikiSource.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Not Applicable

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Not Applicable

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Not Applicable

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– I don't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– I don't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Critical edition generally used today.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Local histories, personal chronicles

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Not Applicable

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yang, 44. "Mulling over Liu T'eng's crime, the empress dowager ordered that his tomb be opened up and his remains be dismembered, so that his soul would have no place to return to."

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– I don't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– I don't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– I don't know

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yang, 40. "On the point of death, the emperor prayed to Buddha, asking that he never be reborn as an emperor." Yang, 230. "The king then said, "If what you said is true, then your country is a Buddha Land. After death I would like to be reincarnated in that country."

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– I don't know

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yang, 230. "The king then said, "If what you said is true, then your country is a Buddha Land. After death I would like to be reincarnated in that country.""

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– I don't know

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– I don't know

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– I don't know

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– No

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yang, 173. "After the emperor's death, a hall for meditation was built on his tomb. Thereafter stupas were sometimes constructed [even] on the graves of the common people"

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– I don't know

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– I don't know

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yang, 223. "In the mountain was a pond wherein an evil dragon lived. A group of three hundred merchants once stopped on the bank of the pond and stayed there, when the dragon, in a fit of anger, inundated [the land around the pond] and drowned the merchants. Upon hearing of this, the king of [Han-]p'an-t'o abdicated in favor of his son, and went to the state of Wu-ch'ang to study the spells of Brahmins. Within four years he had learned all the arts. Upon his return, he resumed his position as king, and went to the pond to exorcise the dragon. The dragon changed itself into a man, and repented before the king."

- ↳ A supreme high-god is present
- No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen
- Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
- I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
- I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
- I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
- I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
- I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
- I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
- I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
- Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life
- I don't know

- ↳ In dreams
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Communicate through other means
 - Specify: Not Applicable

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Yang 231. "To the west of the river was a pond in which a dragon-king lived. On the shore of the pond was a monastery that housed more than fifty monks. Whenever the dragon-king worked his charms, the king would offer prayers and throw gold, jade, and other valuables into the pond. And, when the latter [articles] were washed ashore, he would order the monks to collect them. The monks of the monastery relied on the dragon for a living. Contemporaries called the place the Dragon-king Monastery."

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?
– Yes

↳ In dreams?
– Yes

Notes: Yang 189. "Two years later, [Hou] Ch'ing's wife, a woman of the Ma clan, suddenly dreamed of the image, which told her: "You and your husband have owed me a gilding for so long without [my demanding] recompense. Now I am taking your son, [Hou] Ch'ou-to, as compensation for [your failure to] gild [me]."

↳ In trance possession?
– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices?
– I don't know

↳ Only through religious specialists?
– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch?
– I don't know

↳ Other?
–Specify: Not Applicable

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: Not Applicable

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?
– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?
– I don't know

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?
– No

Are other categories of beings present?
– Mysterious?

Does the text guide divination practices?
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?
– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?
– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– I don't know

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– I don't know

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

Notes: Yang 178: "By the end of the P'u-t'ai period (a.d. 531-532) , Erh-chu T'ienkuang, Prince of Lung-hsi and the Governor of Yung-chou, gathered his army and horses in this temple. Soon afterward, all the gates in the temple collapsed. [Erh-chu] T'ien-kuang,

seeing this, hated it [as a bad omen]. That year he was defeated in a battle and subsequently executed in the eastern marketplace [of Lo-yang]."

- ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Not Applicable

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done only by high god
 - No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - I don't know
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Done randomly
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - I don't know

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
– I don't know

↳ Other?
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?
– I don't know

↳ Consists of good luck?
– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?
– I don't know

↳ Consists of success in battle?
– I don't know

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– I don't know

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– I don't know

↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
– I don't know

↳ Other?
– Specify: Not Applicable

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?
– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?
– I don't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?
– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?
– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?
– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?
– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Yang 35. On the first of the tenth month (November 6), [Erh-chu] Shih-lung and the Princess of Pei-hsiang commandery [Erh-chu Jung's wife], offered sacrifices to the deceased at Prince Feng's Monastery on the Mang Mountains, and donated bolts of silk to the abbot in return for the happiness of the departed."

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– No

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

- ↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?
 - No
- ↳ Are there material offerings present?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they mandatory?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Not Applicable
- ↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?
 - No
- ↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?
 - No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– I don't know

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– I don't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Among other conflicts, it includes chronicles of Erzhu Rong's uprising.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No